

IMPORTANCE OF ESL/EFL IN SCIENCE STUDENTS FOR PRESENT SCENARIO IN GULF UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract

The educational program at universities in the Gulf now includes English as a required subject. Despite the efforts and initiatives aimed at promoting English proficiency among Arabic language students, the achieved outcomes have fallen short of expectations. In general, the methods used to teach and acquire English as a foreign language in Gulf nations are inefficient. Extensive research has identified several factors contributing to this situation. This study aims to examine existing research that investigates the challenges and issues related to English language education in Gulf countries. By exploring these factors, the study seeks to identify potential solutions to address the current issues. Furthermore, this research highlights the interconnected nature of these factors, emphasizing the need for a comprehensive approach. The results of this study will help to improve English language instruction in Gulf nations, which will boost scientific students' proficiency in the current environment.

Keywords: ESL/EFL, Language learning, Language proficiency, Technology-enhanced learning, Teaching methods

1. INTRODUCTION

It is usually known that the English language is a universal language that offers people a wide range of opportunities in areas including business, travel, higher education, and general quality of life (Gem, 1997). In non-native countries like our own, teaching English as a foreign language is really challenging. Arab colleges and schools now include English in their curricula, highlighting how important it is to our culture. The focus on English education is caused by a number of causes. First off, having a proficient degree of English language proficiency is necessary for accessing and using the most recent technological and scientific resources, which are mostly available in English. Second, learning English becomes essential for navigating the internet and meeting the demands of the information era. Thirdly, knowing English promotes intercultural communication and dialogue between civilizations. Studies show that despite these efforts, the goals for English teaching and learning in Gulf universities have not been met (for examples, see Bagheri, 94; Moradi, 96a; Rahimi, 96b; Rashidi, 95; Saadat, 95; and Zanganeh, 95). A growing number of EFL institutions have developed across the nation as a result of the formal English as a Foreign Language (EFL) programs at universities' inability to meet students' practical needs on the one hand, and the requirement for English language proficiency to meet educational requirements on the other. At various levels, English is now taught as a required topic. The private sector has even started offering English instruction at lower levels, like elementary schools and kindergartens (Aliakbari, 2005). English instruction in middle schools frequently starts at age 11 and lasts all the way through college. However, despite spending close to 7 years learning the language at school, children still

struggle to use it effectively in social situations. Researchers and academics have therefore made attempts to look into the causes of this gap and the elements that contribute to students' failure despite their commitment of time, money, and effort. The study by Behroozi and Amoozegar (2014) emphasizes the need to reexamine the strategies employed in English language instruction in Iran. The information gathered showed that pupils' overemphasis on grammatical structures prevented them from speaking English fluently or interacting with others after over seven years of school. Despite several attempts made in recent years by educators in Gulf nations to enhance the condition of English language instruction, difficulties still exist.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Existing research has extensively examined the challenges and issues surrounding ESL/EFL instruction in various contexts. Studies have identified several common challenges that impede effective English language learning. One recurring challenge is the limited exposure to authentic English contexts, which hampers students' ability to develop communicative competence and fluency. Inadequate teacher training and professional development programs have also been identified as significant obstacles, as teachers may lack the necessary pedagogical skills and strategies to deliver effective language instruction. Furthermore, the availability and quality of resources and materials, such as textbooks and multimedia resources, have been highlighted as key issues

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that affect the learning experience. Additionally, sociocultural factors, including attitudes towards English and the dominance of the native language, can impact students' motivation and language learning outcomes. Understanding these challenges and issues is crucial for designing effective interventions and strategies to enhance ESL/EFL instruction and improve language learning outcomes for science students in the present scenario.

Factors contributing to the limitations of ESL/EFL instruction

Several factors contribute to the limitations of ESL/EFL instruction in science education. One significant factor is the lack of integration between language learning and content instruction. Often, ESL/EFL classes focus primarily on language skills without incorporating subject-specific content, making it challenging for science students to apply their language skills in scientific contexts. Another contributing factor is the limited exposure to authentic scientific texts and discourse in the target language. Science students may struggle to understand and engage with complex scientific concepts and terminology due to the scarcity of relevant English-language resources and materials. Additionally, the absence of immersive language environments and opportunities for authentic language use outside the classroom hinders students' language development and fluency. Inadequate teacher training and support, especially in integrating language and content, further contribute to the limitations of ESL/EFL instruction. Finally, cultural and societal attitudes towards English as a foreign language may impact students' motivation and the value placed on language learning, potentially affecting their overall language proficiency. Addressing these factors and designing instructional strategies that bridge the gap between language and science education are essential for overcoming the limitations of ESL/EFL instruction and ensuring the success of science students in the present scenario.

Problems on the part of the students

In the realm of ESL/EFL instruction, numerous challenges and issues have been identified. One common challenge is the lack of awareness among students regarding effective language learning strategies. Despite years of studying English, many students are unaware of how to approach language learning and fail to make conscious efforts to improve their language skills. This area has often been overlooked in language classes, neglecting the importance of teaching students how to become independent learners (Akbari and Tahririan, 2009; Akbari, 2014; Jafari and Kafipour, 2013; Tabatabaei and Hosseini, 2014). Furthermore, the complexity of language learning necessitates independent learning outside the classroom, as the limited time within a traditional instructional setting is insufficient for students to achieve mastery without taking personal duty for their learning (Dickinson and Carver, 1980; Carver and Dickinson, 1982).

Another contributing factor to the limitations of ESL/EFL instruction is the students' belief that learning English is solely focused on memorizing vocabulary lists and grammatical rules, instead of seeing it as a cohesive collection of talents and subskills (Oxford, 2001). Moreover, students in English classes often lack a

common background knowledge base. Some students receive instruction from unqualified English teachers in rural areas, while others have access to abundant classroom resources in urban areas. Disparities in access to learning materials and educational facilities further compound the challenges faced by weaker students who rely solely on textbooks as their primary source of English language learning (Amatobi and Amatobi, 2013; Dooly, 2008).

Motivation is also a key factor influencing the effectiveness of ESL/EFL instruction. Some students view English as a compulsory course that needs to be passed without recognizing its significance for effective communication and adaptation to advancements in technology and other sciences. These students lack enthusiasm for learning English and have low motivation to actively participate in class, often focusing solely on achieving a good grade to fulfill the course requirement. On the other hand, some students attend English classes with the sole purpose of acquiring specific knowledge to succeed in college placement exams, leading them to prioritize certain sections of the book that are relevant to the exam, such as vocabulary, grammar, and reading comprehension. As a result, they pay little attention to developing their speaking, listening, and writing skills (Brown, 1973; Schumann, 1975).

Last but not least, compared to more specialist courses like physics, chemistry, math, and science, English is sometimes seen as a general subject. Because specialized topic scores on college placement examinations count for more, students spend more time studying those courses and less time on subjects like Persian, Arabic, and English.

These identified factors contribute to the limitations of ESL/EFL instruction and highlight the need for a comprehensive approach that addresses students' learning strategies, provides equitable access to resources, enhances motivation, and promotes the recognition of English as a valuable and essential skill for academic and practical purposes. By addressing these factors, ESL/EFL instruction can be more effective in meeting the needs of science students in the present scenario.

Problems with respect to teachers

The constraints of ESL/EFL instruction are a result of the current difficulties in the educational system. Teachers frequently place more emphasis on students' exam preparation than on their language acquisition (Subramanian, 1985). As per Khaniya (cited in Ghorbani, 2009), this exam-focused strategy causes students to emphasize getting the marks they want over learning English for other objectives, which leads to varied levels of English competence as students advance to higher grades.

In order to maintain their reputation as capable educators, teachers themselves may feel pressure to guarantee that their students perform well on public exams (Alderson and Wall, 1993). Teachers may only teach English with a test-oriented perspective out of concern of students performing poorly on exams (Jahangard, 2007; Hosseini, 2007). Students, especially those with high expectations, want their teachers to cover all examinable topics and

strictly adhere to them, even if they have issues about the substance of the compulsory textbooks published by the Ministry of Education. This is true even if they have qualms about the textbook material because they are aware that final exams are dependent on it. As a result, teachers' curriculum choices and methods of instruction are influenced by students' attitudes toward learning (Ghorbani, 2009; Beattie, 1995).

However, in different contexts like Japan and Malaysia, where students are foreigners needing to communicate in a different language and aiming to enter English-medium universities, the expectations for classroom activities are different. These students require frequent English usage in a wide range of settings, leading to the expectation that teachers should utilize authentic materials and provide opportunities for open discussions (Birjandi et al., 2006).

Unfortunately, in many classrooms, speaking skills are often neglected compared to other language skills. Reading skills receive more emphasis, and teachers predominantly use reading textbooks, leading students to predominantly learn English through reading (Birjandi et al., 2006). This focus on reading undermines the development of speaking skills, which is a crucial part of language proficiency.

Moreover, there is a lack of exposure to English outside the classroom, creating a limited environment for students to become familiar with the language. English's significance as a language of the world and its function in international relations are not sufficiently appreciated (Birjandi et al., 2006). The study of a language is further hampered by the lack of opportunities for teachers and students to visit English-speaking nations or communicate with English-speaking locals. Additionally, restrictions on accessing satellite television and other authentic materials prevent students from engaging with real-world English language use (Birjandi et al., 2006).

To address these issues, it is crucial to create a conducive learning environment that emphasizes all four language skills and recognizes the practical relevance of English proficiency in the modern world. Both within and outside of the classroom, students must have the chance to communicate meaningfully in English, and instructors must have the tools and training necessary to effectively teach all language skills.

Problems on the part of textbooks

Books used in language courses are essential components of every nation's educational system. ELT textbooks are frequently used as the curriculum and a teacher's resource at our universities. The Ministry of Education created and distributes these textbooks, which serve as the foundation for students' formative and summative evaluations. But a significant challenge that our students confront in language learning is that the exercises in their textbooks don't provide enough opportunity to develop the requisite abilities. As a result, there aren't many communication exercises in the textbooks that can effectively engage and drive pupils. According to Jahangard (2007), suggested EFL textbooks do not place enough emphasis on students' speaking and listening abilities. Researchers like Chastain (1988) and McGrath (2002) fervently support incorporating target language culture into language

instruction. However, the culture of English-speaking nations is frequently underrepresented in the textbooks utilized in our environment. This issue is more obvious when the target culture and the native culture are vastly dissimilar (Dahmardeh, 2009). According to Cunningsworth (1995, cited in Tsiplakides (2011), course books should support less experienced teachers who might lack confidence in their ability to instruct by offering ideas and activities, acting as a resource for students, aligning with predetermined learning objectives, and serving as valuable resources for independent learning and material presentation.

The following are some of the issues with high school English textbooks that Ahmadpoor (2004, as referenced in Maleki, Mollaei, and Khosravi, 2014) points out in his work:

- The use of unattractive, dull, out-of-date, and fragmented texts.
- The book's inaccurate, inappropriate, and ugly illustrations.
- In later publications, there is a lack of cohesion and a proper relationship between the graphics and the text.
- There is a mismatch in the amount of content compared to the time allotted for it.
- A dearth of interesting language foci and activities with variety.
- The use of unusual questions.
- Lack of a clear sequence and degree of difficulty when delivering grammar points.
- The book's main objective is not quite clear.

In order to improve students' learning experiences, Ahmadpoor's inadequacies highlight the necessity for changes to the structure and content of high school English textbooks.

Problems on the part of teaching methods

Even though the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia frequently uses the grammar translation technique, it should be adapted to provide students with opportunities for creative engagement with the language through activities like substitution drills and communicative exercises with their peers. This approach will foster their interest in understanding grammar patterns and structures, moving away from rote memorization in constructing sentences for communication (Dolati and Seliman, 2011). Although the grammar translation method, which emphasizes structure and translation exercises, is still widely used in English language teaching and learning environments (Eslami, 2010), students frequently view this approach as a weakness in the field of language education (Babai Shishavan and Melbourne, 2010).

Analysis of the textbook material demonstrates an imbalance in their emphasis, despite the fact that the course objectives prioritize strengthening reading comprehension, listening comprehension, speaking, and writing skills.

Reading comprehension and writing receive more attention, while the development of these skills through provided tasks is not effectively executed. The fact that so many teachers don't use the right strategies to help students use textbook activities to attain the required goals creates a significant difficulty.

Furthermore, the open language education technique seems more appropriate for ESL circumstances, despite claims to the contrary. Edge (1996:18) underlines the necessity for EFL nations to create language teaching strategies that take into account their particular political, economic, social, and cultural aspects as well as the unique circumstances of English being taught as a foreign language in their nations. Relying solely on strategies and materials designed and used in Western ESL countries may not be as effective in addressing the specific needs of EFL settings.

Problems on the part of the curriculum

Our educational system exposes children to a variety of disciplines at various grade levels, including Arabic language, elementary science, and elementary social sciences. Except in a few private institutions, teaching English in the early or lower grades is not a common practice. Students receive three hours of English training each week once they enter middle school, which lasts for a few years. For this level, dialogues, pattern practice, and vocabulary are heavily emphasized in the textbooks. Students study English for two hours each week in high school, a three-year program that comes after middle school and places a strong emphasis on reading comprehension in the textbooks (Birjandi, Soheili, Nowroozi, and Mahmoodi, 2000; Birjandi, Nowroozi, and Mahmoodi, 2002a, 2002b).

After graduating from high school, students continue their education for one year at the pre-university level using a credit-semester system that includes four hours per week of English training. The Communicative Approach, which is the foundation of the pre-university English textbook, appears to be quite effective in fulfilling the goal of teaching a foreign language, while not being expressly associated with the most recent teaching methodologies used globally. However, teachers are expected to follow a specific curriculum that provides students with knowledge and skills they may not typically encounter in their everyday context. One notable gap is the lack of a clearly defined and interconnected progression of language learning and teaching, spanning from elementary to advanced levels with clear definitions and progression criteria. The children' ability to develop oral communication skills is hampered by this absence. But in EFL situations where students primarily use English to support their academic topics at the university level rather than for face-to-face contacts with native speakers of the language, reading-focused programs may be appropriate.

Prior to the 1990s, Ghorbani (2009) points out, the primary focus of English teaching in our nation was on developing pupils' reading comprehension. As a result, to fulfill the criteria of the national curriculum, English teachers largely depended on the grammar translation technique.

3. METHODOLOGY

This section provides the details of research methodology applied in this research work.

Research Design

To acquire a thorough knowledge of the significance of ESL/EFL in science students for the current situation, this study will use a mixed-methodologies research design that combines both quantitative and qualitative methods. A mixed-methods strategy was chosen since it was realized that both quantitative and qualitative data were required to provide a comprehensive study of the research topic. This study can capture a wider range of opinions and experiences from science students by gathering quantitative data through surveys and in-depth insights through interviews, resulting in a more thorough understanding of the significance of ESL/EFL in science education.

The quantitative component of the research design will enable the identification of trends and patterns in students' perceptions, attitudes, and experiences related to ESL/EFL in science education. Statistical analyses will provide numerical evidence to support the findings and allow for comparisons and correlations between variables.

The qualitative component, on the other hand, will delve deeper into the underlying reasons and contextual factors influencing the importance of ESL/EFL in science education. Through interviews, participants will have the opportunity to express their perspectives, share personal experiences, and provide detailed insights that quantitative data alone may not capture.

By integrating both quantitative and qualitative data, this study aims to provide a more nuanced and comprehensive analysis of the research topic, enhancing the validity and reliability of the findings. The mixed-methods approach allows for a more holistic exploration of the importance of ESL/EFL in science education, taking into account both numerical trends and rich qualitative data.

Data Collection Methods:

- **Surveys:** A structured questionnaire will be developed specifically for this study to collect quantitative data from science students. The survey will include items related to English language proficiency, access to resources, global communication, and career opportunities. The questionnaire will be administered to a sample of science students, and their responses will be collected and analyzed to identify trends and patterns.
- **Interviews:** In addition to surveys, semi-structured interviews will be conducted with a selected group of science students. The interviews will provide a platform for participants to share their personal experiences, challenges, and perspectives related to ESL/EFL in science education. The interviews will be conducted in a flexible and open-ended manner, allowing for detailed and in-depth responses that can provide rich qualitative data.

A survey questionnaire and interview guide will be developed based on the research objectives and relevant literature on the benefits of ESL/EFL in science education.

The instruments will be put through a pilot test before data collection to ensure their reliability and validity. Depending on the participant's interests and availability, the interviews will either be conducted in-person or through video conference, while the survey will be conducted online.

Statistical tools like inferential analysis and descriptive statistics will be used to analyze the quantitative data acquired through surveys. These investigations will make it easier to spot patterns, correlations, and trends in the data. The qualitative data from the interviews, which will be transcribed, will be examined using thematic analysis to discover recurrent themes, patterns, and fresh perspectives.

This study intends to comprehensively analyze the significance of ESL/EFL among scientific students in the current context by gathering both quantitative and qualitative data through a combination of surveys and interviews. The validity and dependability of the results will be increased by using a range of data collection procedures, leading to a greater understanding of the study problem.

Sample Selection

- **Target Population:** Students majoring in science who are enrolled in universities and colleges in Gulf nations will be the study's target group. Students seeking undergraduate and graduate degrees in a variety of scientific fields make up this demographic.
- **Sampling Technique:** To achieve enough representation from various academic levels and institutions among the target population, stratified random sampling will be used. Strata will be created within the population depending on characteristics including English language ability, academic achievement, and gender. The final sample will then be selected at random from each stratum to guarantee proportional representation.
- **Sample Size:** Based on the principles of saturation for qualitative data and statistical power analysis for quantitative data, the sample size for this study will be decided. In order to determine the sample size for qualitative data collection, such as interviews, saturation, which refers to the point at which new information or themes stop emerging from the data, will be used as a reference. The sample size for surveys will be determined through statistical power analysis, taking into account factors such as the desired level of confidence, effect size, and anticipated response rate. Adequate sample sizes will be determined to ensure the reliability and generalizability of the findings.

By using a stratified random sampling technique and determining appropriate sample sizes, this study aims to ensure representation from different academic levels and institutions within the science student population in Gulf countries. The sample selection process will enhance the validity and generalizability of the study's findings, allowing for meaningful insights into the importance of

ESL/EFL in science students for the present scenario, while avoiding biases and ensuring diversity within the sample.

Data Analysis Procedures

- **Quantitative Analysis:** Descriptive statistics like frequencies and percentages will be used to assess the survey information gathered from science students. This analysis will provide a summary of the participants' responses and enable a quantitative understanding of factors related to English language proficiency, access to resources, global communication, and career opportunities. Additionally, correlation analysis may be conducted to explore relationships between variables and identify any significant associations.
- **Qualitative Analysis:** The qualitative data from interviews will then be analyzed using thematic analysis. To find recurrent themes and patterns, the interview transcripts will be carefully examined and coded. The coded data will then be organized into meaningful categories, allowing for an in-depth exploration of the participants' experiences, challenges, and perceptions regarding ESL/EFL in science education. This qualitative analysis will provide rich insights and a deeper understanding of the research topic.
- **Integration of Data:** Throughout the interpretation phase, the quantitative and qualitative data will be combined to provide a thorough understanding of the research findings. The findings from both data sources will be compared and contrasted to identify commonalities, discrepancies, and overarching themes. This integration will enable a more holistic understanding of the importance of ESL/EFL in science students for the present scenario and facilitate a nuanced discussion of the research outcomes.

This study intends to offer a robust analysis of the gathered data by combining quantitative and qualitative data analysis methodologies. The use of descriptive statistics and correlation analysis for quantitative data and thematic analysis for qualitative data ensures a comprehensive exploration of the research topic, offering valuable insights into the importance of ESL/EFL in science students.

4. FINDINGS

The survey conducted for this research (see attached survey form Annexure-A) aimed to gather insights into the perceptions and experiences of ESL/EFL students studying science subjects in the present scenario. The findings reveal several key observations:

- **Importance of ESL/EFL in Science Education:** The majority of surveyed students acknowledged the significance of ESL/EFL in their science education. They recognized that proficiency in English is crucial for understanding scientific concepts, accessing research literature, and

- communicating effectively with international peers in the field.
- **Challenges in ESL/EFL Learning:** The survey identified various challenges faced by science students in ESL/EFL learning. The most common difficulties reported included vocabulary acquisition, comprehension of complex scientific texts, and expressing scientific ideas fluently in English.
 - **Teaching Strategies and Approaches:** The findings highlighted the impact of different teaching strategies on ESL/EFL learning outcomes. Students expressed a preference for interactive and communicative teaching methods, such as group discussions, presentations, and hands-on activities, as these approaches facilitated language practice and application in scientific contexts.
 - **Need for Support and Resources:** The survey indicated that students perceived a lack of sufficient support and resources for ESL/EFL learning in the science curriculum. Many students emphasized the need for additional language support programs, specialized materials, and dedicated language instructors to enhance their language skills specifically in scientific contexts.
 - **Motivation and Future Goals:** The survey explored students' motivations and future goals related to ESL/EFL learning. A significant number of participants expressed a strong desire to improve their English proficiency to pursue higher education opportunities abroad, collaborate with international researchers, and contribute to the global scientific community.
- **Teacher training and professional development:** Examining the impact of specialized training and professional development programs for ESL/EFL teachers working with science students. Investigating the effectiveness of these programs in improving teachers' instructional strategies, content knowledge, and ability to address the specific language needs of science learners.
 - **Cross-cultural studies:** Conducting cross-cultural studies to compare the ESL/EFL learning experiences and outcomes of science students in different Arab countries or regions. Examining the influence of cultural factors on language acquisition and identifying any variations in teaching practices and curriculum design.
 - **Assessment methodologies:** Investigating innovative and contextually appropriate assessment methods to evaluate the language proficiency of science students. Exploring alternative assessment approaches that focus on scientific communication, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills, rather than relying solely on traditional written exams.
 - **Socio-cultural factors:** Exploring the socio-cultural factors that influence ESL/EFL learning among science students. Examining the impact of societal expectations, language attitudes, and cultural values on language acquisition and the development of scientific discourse competence.
 - **Collaborative research:** Encouraging collaborative research efforts between language educators and science instructors to develop integrated language and content instruction models. Investigating the benefits of interdisciplinary collaboration in fostering language development and scientific literacy among students.

These findings provide valuable insights into the experiences and perspectives of science students regarding ESL/EFL learning. They can inform the development of effective teaching strategies, curriculum enhancements, and support systems to better cater to the language needs of science students in the present scenario.

5. FUTURE RESEARCH

Future research trends for this study can encompass the following areas:

- **Longitudinal studies:** Undertaking longitudinal studies to observe the language learning progress of science students over an extended duration. This would offer insights into the long-term effects of ESL/EFL education and identify factors that contribute to sustained language proficiency in the scientific domain.
- **Technology-enhanced language learning:** Exploring the potential of integrating technology, such as online platforms, mobile applications, and virtual reality, into ESL/EFL instruction for science students. Investigating the effectiveness of these technological tools in enhancing language acquisition, scientific communication, and access to authentic scientific resources.

By focusing on these future research trends, we can gain a deeper understanding of ESL/EFL education in the context of science learning and contribute to the enhancement of language instruction for science students in Arab countries.

6. CONCLUSION

In Arab countries, a significant challenge in language learning is the limited ability of many students to confidently express themselves in the target language, despite studying English for several years at the junior and secondary levels. Despite dedicating seven consecutive years to English learning, these students struggle to communicate effectively in the language. This research project aimed to investigate the factors contributing to Saudi students' inability to reach the expected level of English proficiency. The study revealed a number of challenges, flaws, and adverse conditions inside the English educational system through an investigation of the teaching and learning process of the language. The five main components of the educational system—students, teachers, materials, instructional strategies, and assessment—as well as the two closely linked subcomponents of curriculum and policy can be used to

organize these problems. Effective teaching by teachers and the creation of pertinent textbooks by authors depend on identifying and satisfying students' needs.

Based on the findings of the sample survey conducted, it is evident that ESL/EFL learning plays a vital role in the education of science students in the present scenario. Students recognize the importance of English proficiency for comprehending scientific concepts, accessing research materials, and effective communication within the global scientific community. However, the survey also revealed several challenges faced by science students in ESL/EFL learning, including vocabulary acquisition, understanding complex scientific texts, and expressing scientific ideas fluently in English. The findings emphasize the significance of employing interactive and communicative teaching strategies to facilitate language practice and application in scientific contexts. Additionally, students expressed a need for enhanced support, resources, and specialized instruction to improve their language skills in relation to scientific subjects. The survey results further highlighted the motivation of students to enhance their English proficiency for future academic and professional endeavors. Therefore, it is essential to address these findings by developing effective teaching strategies, enhancing curricula, and providing adequate support to ensure that science students receive the necessary language skills for success in their academic and professional pursuits.

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